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Coordination and Support Actions

SONNETS

***SOcietal Needs aNalysis and Emerging Technologies
in the public Sector***

Deliverable D4.4

Stakeholder specific recommendations

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Abstract:	SONNETS issues a policy brief informing policy makers about necessary research needs to transform the public sector in an efficient and citizen-friendly service, a research brief to inform researchers about research needs and a technology brief to inform representatives of the public sector about emerging ICT technologies and their impact on their day-to-day work.

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Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Title
ICT	Information and communication technology
NLP	Natural language processing
SWOT	Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats
WBAT	Weighted Bit Assessment Table

Table 1: Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Executive Summary

The deliverable at hand contains the final results of SONNETS in form of stakeholder tailored recommendation briefs. In total, it contains three briefs for three different stakeholder groups:

1. A policy brief to inform policy makers about:
 - a. Necessary research and non-research activities to implement successfully the identified emerging ICTs in the public sector pursuing the aim to satisfy societal and public sector needs
 - b. Methodological recommendations regarding how to innovate the public sector with emerging ICTs and developing technology roadmaps
 - c. Content-related recommendations regarding pressing societal and public sector needs as well as emerging ICTs with the potential to innovate the public sector
2. A research brief to inform researchers about:
 - a. Technological and socio-economic research needs
3. A technology brief to inform public sector personnel about:
 - a. Emerging ICTs with the potential to innovate the public sector and their strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats

1 Introduction

On the basis of the work of WP4 and the feedback of the validation workshops, a set of user tailored recommendation briefs has been designed to inform the different stakeholders about the needs of the citizens and the public sector, emerging ICT technologies and its potential applications which could modernize the public sector, as well as the necessary technological and socio-economic research activities.

Thus, the following briefs have been designed:

- A **policy brief** to inform policy makers about the necessary research needs to transform the public sector in an efficient and citizen-friendly service of the future.
- A **research brief** to inform researchers about the actual technological and socio-economic research needs of the end-user.
- A **technology brief** to inform representatives of the public sector about new emerging ICT technologies and how these could improve the efficiency, simplify the processes and services of their day-to-day work and also help to transform the public sector to be more open and citizen-friendly.

The overall aim is to improve the collaboration of researchers, policy makers and the public sector in order to mutually stimulate each other to create new and better end-user specific solutions in a faster way.

2 Policy brief

SONNETS pursued the aim to meet the need for a better, more efficient, effective and quality delivering public service. This does not only imply transforming the public sector itself and covering the needs of public sector employees and policy makers, but it will also have a positive impact on citizens and businesses, that will in turn accelerate the EU economy and improve quality of life.

To meet this aim, SONNETS has developed two different types of outputs or findings during the course of the project:

First, the consortium has presented, tested and validated a **methodological framework** on how to innovate the public sector with emerging ICT's with the objective to satisfy societal and public sector needs.

Second, it has produced, discussed and validated **content** in terms of a list of priority societal and public sector needs, a list of emerging ICT with the potential to innovate the public sector and also a list of necessary technological and non-technological activities to implement these emerging technologies successfully into the public sector.

We will therefore present in the next chapters two different types of recommendations:

- Methodological recommendations (*How to innovate the public sector?*)
- Content-related recommendations (*What are the priority needs? Which emerging ICTs are suitable and have a high impact? What activities are needed?*)

1.1 Methodological recommendations

Methodologically SONNETS has designed an approach that will accelerate the modernization of the public sector through the identification and analysis of emerging technologies that hold the potential to transform the public sector into a technology leader and innovation carrier, addressing, at the same time the most pressing needs of the society.

Recommendation 1

(Regarding the innovation identification framework):

During the course of SONNETS the consortium has presented, tested, adapted and validated an **innovation identification framework** for collecting, analyzing and cross-checking the usability of emerging ICTs in the public sector.

We recommend this framework as a self-standing methodological aid for supporting the public sector's ICT transformation.

The **SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework** is a methodological framework that will accelerate the transformation of the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The overall process is presented in Figure 1.

The **SONNETS Framework** relies on seven logical steps or phases as follows:

- i) the identification of societal needs, societal and public sector trends/challenges
- ii) the identification of technologies and trends that make a difference in other sectors
- iii) the selection of a subset of these technologies and trends, and the analysis of the latter in terms of their key characteristics and specificities
- iv) the assessment of these techs in domains originally met and their correlation to the public sector needs and societal challenges
- v) the evaluation of the latter's' innovation potential in terms of impact and feasibility
- vi) the selection of those that make more sense to be ported to the public sector
- vii) the evaluation and ratification of the overall findings

Figure 1: SONNETS innovation identification framework

Recommendation 2

(regarding the identification of societal and public sector needs):

Qualitative approaches to identify societal and public sector needs are a valuable method to help outlining public sector innovation activities, which are demand-driven and need-based.

However, care has to be taken that the needs identification follows a crowdsource approach and contains validation and prioritization processes. The caveat of this qualitative approach (to produce only a subjective, but meaningful representation) should be borne in mind.

One aim of SONNETS was to identify current and emerging societal challenges and trends that will have to be tackled by the public sector and subsequently analyse and map these challenges to the different policy domains in order to identify public sector innovation requirements.

The research methodology for identifying societal needs comprises of four key phases: In the first phase, a **literature review** has been undertaken. During this phase, the needs of society, businesses and the public sector have been identified and summarized to a long list of needs, which subsequently has been clustered, revised and refined. The first phase also aimed to highlight the current societal trends and

challenges relevant for each stakeholder group. In the second phase, **experts' interviews** were used to validate and prioritize these needs. The third phase consisted of a **focus group** to fine-tune and refine the results and develop possible innovation actions that could be employed to meet those needs. Finally, in the fourth phase a set of **validation activities** were conducted in the four countries involved in the project (Italy, Spain, Greece and Germany) and also via an online consultation. The main objectives were to understand the relevance of the needs identified at local level, identify potential contextual barriers or key success factors for implementation and finally to single out which policy domains were most relevant for the solution of the identified problems.

From a methodological standpoint, the **key lessons learned** throughout the process of needs identifications are the following:

The first phase (desk-based/secondary research) highlighted the critical role of a *crowdsource approach* (shared between the consortium and the expert committee) in carrying out a desk research deeply rooted in the relevant literature for identifying needs as well as for highlighting societal and public sector trends and challenges. This phase also played a pivotal role in identifying innovation solutions to meet the innovation requirements of public sector for each need and extracting information about relevant examples and case studies across Europe. This helped to situate our results in the current EU initiatives and projects that work on similar issues of public sector innovation and societal trends/challenges/needs.

The subsequent phases (2 and 3) assisted our efforts at triangulating data and information from different sources and *verifying the authenticity* of the

information collected through multiple sources. Finally, phase 4 was vital to further *prioritize* and *contextualize* needs and potential solutions.

It is important to highlight **two caveats** of this process. The first has to do with the fact that a *qualitative approach* was selected. Thus, the representation of reality depicted should be considered similar to a painting, that is to say: a subjective yet meaningful representation of reality without any ambition of statistical representativeness. The second has to do with the *prevalence of Southern European countries* in the consortium (three out of four). Such unbalance influenced in the perception of the public sector emerged from the consultation activities conducted.

Recommendation 3

(Regarding the roadmap development process):

SONNETS has designed a **roadmap development process** building on other market-pull & technology-push approaches and using the multi-criteria assessment tool WBAT [1, 2].

The different steps of the process have been validated by the experts committee and also during the SONNETS validation workshop.

We therefore recommend this process as a methodological aid for developing research and technology roadmaps.

SONNETS had the aim to base its recommendations on societal and public sector needs and also on emerging ICTs which could potentially innovate the public sector. Therefore, it made sense to use a roadmap approach which is based both on needs (or on the 'market' in the business language) and also on available technologies on the other side. Thus, the SONNETS roadmap incorporates the general idea of the **EIRMA (European Industrial Research Management Association) [1] approach** of including both market-pull as well as technology-push aspects into the development of the roadmap.

In SONNETS we had to make some adaptations to this generic roadmap, due to the fact that our roadmap is not intended to be used in a company, but as a recommendation on how to innovate the public sector with emerging ICTs. Thus the final roadmaps contain information regarding necessary technology R&D activities or rather suggestions for adaptations, modifications or enhancements, actions in the public sector itself (like training, infrastructure, processes..) and also necessary measurements to deal with ethical, legal and societal challenges. Methodologically, we followed a three step approach, which is based on other roadmap development processes like the one from EIRMA [1] or the T-plan approach [2]

First step: This step contains an analysis of emerging ICTs regarding their technology-readiness level, current research projects, actors and existing and potential applications, solutions and services of these technologies in the public sector and also in other domains.

Second step: In this step we changed the perspective and set the focus on the societal and public sector needs. Each need has been assigned to one or more emerging ICTs, which have the potential to satisfy the need when implemented in the public sector. For each technology assigned to a specific need a to-do list has been developed containing a list of all necessary research and non-research activities needed to implement and use this technology successfully in the public sector. Methodologically, this was done by using the Weighted Bit Assessment Table (WBAT) method [3, 4] developed by Fraunhofer INT.

Third step: In this step these to-do lists have been filled with life. For each emerging ICT one societal, business or public sector need has been selected, for which this technology has the highest impact. This technology-need matching has been validated during an expert's workshop. For each of these technology-need combinations a roadmap has been developed containing information regarding the current state of the art and existing applications and also necessary technological and non-technological activities to implement these technologies successfully in the public sector.

Figure 2: SONNETS roadmap developing process

1.2 Content-related recommendations

Content-wise, SONNETS has produced a list of priority societal and public sector needs, a list of emerging ICTs and trends with the potential to innovate the public sector as well as a compilation of necessary technological and non-technological activities regarding how to implement these emerging ICTs into the public sector.

Recommendation 4

(Regarding societal, business and public sector needs):

The qualitative approach of SONNETS to identify societal and public sector in the four countries of the consortium has shown both the **heterogeneity in the perception** as well as some level of convergence regarding a limited number of needs. These **shared priority needs** are 'inclusive well-being and health', an 'increase in the resource productivity within the public sector', the pivotal role of 'human capital' and also the need for 'political participation' of the citizens. We would thus recommend starting European-wide actions to deal with these shared needs.

To summarize the results of the SONNETS activities regarding the identification of societal, business and public sector needs, it is helpful to consider two different points of view. The first point of view may be situated outside the public sector and combines the perspectives of citizens, businesses and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Such stakeholders would like to see the process of public sector innovation unfold along three main dimensions:

- **Simplicity:** of laws and regulations, of interfaces for the interaction with the different public agencies.
- **Accountability:** in terms of response times (a key factor

in mission and life critical processes) and of allocation of scarce public resources

- **Inclusiveness:** to balance social inequality and for the engagement of local stakeholder in the definition of policy priorities.

The second point of view, instead, may be positioned within the public sector and proposes the following key dimensions as a compass to orient the process of public sector reform:

- **Meritocracy:** through the creation of incentive systems for employees to shoulder the risk connected with innovation activities as well as through the implementation of performance-based reward systems.
- **Agility:** promoted through an injection of fresh energies in the form of new and young personnel as well as through an ambitious training program for older workers.
- **Coordination:** with the private sector that, due to the shrinking of public budgets, is playing an increasing important role in the provision of services of public utility.

As it is possible to note from the situation depicted above, the complexity of the issues to be solved goes well beyond what a technological solution may offer. In

this respect, **technology should be considered as one ingredient of a more elaborated recipe.**

Finally, **human capital** was clearly identified as a core and cross-country issue for a successful implementation from both the demand and the supply side of public sector innovation. In this respect, any technological implementation should aim at being transparent to stakeholders both inside and outside the public sector. In other words, the innovative solutions should try to hide their complexity in order to reduce internal resistance to change and to promote an easier and widespread adoption among potential external users.

STAKEHOLDER	KEY PRIORITY NEED
INDIVIDUALS/SOCIETY	Inclusive well-being and health
	Faster access to public services
	Political participation
	Education & training
	Paperless state
BUSINESSES	Easy access to public sector information
	Stimulate an entrepreneurial and start-up culture
	Access to funds
	Simplifying recruitment procedures
	Talent acquisition and retention
PUBLIC SECTOR	Increase resources productivity
	Employees remuneration and incentives
	Improve access to public services
	Civil servants as a community of change
	Recruitment and training

Table 2: Key Priority Needs in the four countries of the SONNETS consortium (Spain, Italy, Greece and Germany)

Recommendation 5

(Regarding emerging ICTs with the potential to innovate the public sector):

SONNETS has identified, selected and assessed emerging ICTs with the potential to innovate the public sector. The **list of technologies and trends** recommended for the implementation in the public sector are presented in the SONNETS Technology brief (see chapter 4) along with the strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the respective technologies.

Within the network of SONNETS especially big data and data analytics, cloud computing, signatures, artificial intelligence and open data are seen as the most important technologies and trends that could impact the public sector in the following five years.

The adaption and utilisation of emerging ICTs, especially in the case of the Public Sector, is highly related with a **time horizon** that demonstrates the maturity and applicability of technologies in different domains.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 present a conceptual hype curve regarding the technologies and trends identified within SONNETS with regard to their **maturity and applicability** as seen from the public sector's perspective. These hype curves are based on information that derives from the current trends of the ICT (in general) and of the ICT domain and also on the views that have been recorded during the brainstorming activities, the focus groups and the interviews that took place during the course of SONNETS. One should consider that the placement of each element on the curve has been performed having in mind both the mature and the immature sub-areas it contains and how these are considered from the view of the public sector, where already established and widely used technologies are more preferable.

Figure 3: Hype Curve of identified ICTs for supporting public sector innovation

Figure 4: Hype Curve of identified ICT trends for supporting public sector innovation

Recommendation 6

(Regarding necessary technological and non-technological activities to implement emerging ICTs in the public sector):

The necessary technological and non-technological activities to implement emerging ICTs in the public sector are presented in the SONNETS research brief (see chapter 'Research brief').

3 Research brief

SONNETS had the overall aim to develop a roadmap of necessary research, innovation and implementation activities to modernize the public sector with emerging ICTs and addressing thereby related societal challenges.

Thus, the final recommendations of SONNETS base both on societal and public sector needs as well as on our analysis of emerging ICTs which could potentially innovate the public sector.

For each of the 23 technologies and trends identified in the course of the project, we have developed a one-page summary of recommendations. Each of these one-pagers contains an emerging technology or trend and the suggestions to implement this technology with the aim to satisfy a specific societal, business or public sector need.

For each of these technology-need combinations a set of technological and non-technological activities have been developed, which should be performed when implementing these technologies in the public sector.

Recommendation 1:

Using 'artificial intelligence and bots' to meet the business need 'Access to public sector information'

Status quo:

In general it can be observed that artificial intelligence is one of the top emerging technologies in which a lot of research and development is happening right now.

However, the state of the art of artificial intelligence already permits to have several applications which could help to satisfy the need to access public sector information.

There are currently many administrations, like Enfield Council, the Department of Homeland Security, North Carolina's Innovation Center, the Australian Tax Office or the government of Singapore which use artificial intelligence in the form of chatbots to interact with their citizens.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Natural communications between artificial intelligence systems and humans
- Advancement in natural language processing (e.g. regarding local language)
- Learn and reason of artificial intelligence systems, as they encounter new tasks and situations
- 'cold user' experience; lack of personality of artificial intelligence systems

Non-technical challenges:

- *Personnel*: need for well-educated and trained personnel
- *Personnel strategy*: Prepare a long-term plan regarding the future of the current personnel (new tasks and possible displacements)
- *Chatbot infrastructure*: infrastructure provider or one's own IT infrastructure
- *Promotion and dealing with public acceptance issues*
- *Cyber security issues*: e.g. regarding hacker and scammers
- *Regulations and laws*: e.g. in the area of ethics, liability, intellectual property, security, privacy, dignity and autonomy.

Recommendation 2:

Using '*augmented reality*' to meet the societal need '*Experiential education and training*'

Status quo:

According to Gartner his augmented reality (AR) belongs to the key technology trends and is showing promise in delivering a high degree of competitive advantage over the next five to 10 years. But already now there are a lot of augmented reality apps for the classroom, which are also in use in some schools. In the French curriculum augmented reality is already recommended to be used in middle school.

Also more specialized AR systems for university students or in the automotive or printing industry exist. In a military environment AR has been used since 2009.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Stability of the marker-less tracking technique
- Recognition algorithms for human forms
- AR environment development tools (usability; still high technical knowledge and considerable time is needed to generate educational content)

Non-technical challenges:

- *Educational programs*: they have to be re-designed from scratch with the possibilities of AR fully in mind
- *Training*: the teacher have to be trained in the usage of augmented reality
- *Regulations*: e.g. regarding privacy and intellectual property rights
- *cyber security issues*: have to be dealt with (e.g. hacker attacks, exfiltration of personal or behavioral data, privacy risks, risk of the introduction of malicious applications)

Recommendation 3:

Using 'big-data and data analytics' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Status quo:

Big Data technologies will definitely open new opportunities and enable breakthroughs related to healthcare data analytics addressing different perspectives: (i) descriptive to answer what happened, (ii) diagnostic to answer the reason why it happened, (iii) predictive to understand what will happen and (iv) prescriptive to detect how we can make it happen.

There are already many examples for the application of big data analytics in health care up and running ranging from applications for asthma patients, treatments for cancer patients, rare diseases, to the personnel planning in emergency rooms.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- data quality and cleaning of data
- Data quantity (dealing with the large volume and velocity of data; including new data sources)
- Dealing with multi-modal data
- Data access (to different isolated data silos)
- Healthcare knowledge (include the knowledge of the healthcare professionals)
- Analytical methods (constantly improve and update existing analytical methods)

Non-technical challenges:

- *Personnel*: with sufficient technical expertise
- *Training*: digital training and education programs
- *Data storage*: (e.g. cloud-storage) and cross-border exchange
- *Strategic changes*: change the health care organizations to become data driven
- *Promotion*: deal with issues regarding the acceptance of big data/ data analytics
- *Regulations*: regarding the privacy and security of patient data
- *Good practice*: of data governance
- *Common standards*: across the big data value chain (addressing the issues of interoperability)

Recommendation 4:

Using 'biometrics' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Status quo:

Biometric methods are used in many different areas of applications. The solutions and systems available on the market are able to serve a broad range regarding performance, security, usability and standard conformance.

Many EU countries already use biometric identity cards (e.g. Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands) or biometric visa programs. Some EU countries use biometric ID cards for social security systems, requesting car licence plates or conducting tax declarations.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Identifying the best feature representation scheme for a given biometric trait
- Designing robust matcher for a given representation scheme
- Handling poor quality biometric samples
- Improving the distinctiveness of biometric traits
- Improving the persistence of biometric traits
- Unconstrained biometric sensing environment
- System security and user privacy

Non-technical challenges:

- *Infrastructure:* Provide for the necessary infrastructure/hardware (sensor, processor, storage)
- *Change of processes:* Adapt the public processes to the usage of biometric systems
- *Cyber security:* Deal with cyber security and data protection issues

Recommendation 5:

Using '*blockchain technology*' to meet the societal need '*Faster and transparent access to public sector services*'.

Status quo:

There are many possible ways that blockchains can make government more accountable, transparent, efficient and fraud-proof, which include contract management, electronic voting and health care. There are already several pilot projects in different countries regarding the use of block chain technology in e-health, e-resident systems, elections and especially land and property registration. A prominent country which has already several applications of blockchain technology in use is Estonia. Other countries include for example Sweden, Hong Kong, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria or Georgia. However, despite these pilot projects blockchain technology is still in its infancy, so that there are still unknown factors and vulnerabilities.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- to provide a balance between privacy and confidentiality on the one side and transparency on the other side
- resolve challenges such as transaction speed, the verification process and data limits
- provide high-performance, low-latency operations
- ensure that distributed ledgers are scalable, secure and provide proof of correctness of their contents
- energy efficiency
- ensure high level of cryptography

Non-technical challenges:

- *Personnel*: Recruit or train personnel in blockchain technology
- *Infrastructure*: blockchain-as-a-service or another infrastructure solutions?
- *General strategy*: Develop a strategy for shifting the public sector processes towards placing trust and authority in a decentralized network
- *Cyber security issues*: e.g. Sybil-attacks and distributed denial of service attacks)
- *Legal issues*: arising from the use of blockchain technology in the public sector on governmental level
- *Economics*: Consider the economic pro and cons

Recommendation 6:

Using 'cloud computing' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Status quo:

There are already many cloud providers available, like e.g.

- Public clouds (e.g. Google docs, Microsoft Office 365, SAP Business by Design)
- Private Clouds
- Hybrid Clouds (have elements of private and public cloud)
- Infrastructure as a service (IaaS) (e.g. Amazon Web Services, Google Compute Engine, Windows Azure)
- Platform as a service (PaaS) (e.g. Google App Engine, Amazon Elastic Beanstalk)
- Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) (e.g. from Microsoft, Google, Salesforce.com, Cisco, Intuit)

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Provision of IT infrastructure where necessary

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training*: Educating staff and the general public on the underlying technology, its use and advantages.
- *Creating/adapting legislation*: to address privacy and security concerns, and to create clear rules for service providers.
- *Adapt internal public service procedures*: to make full use of cloud computing.
- *Co-work with industry*: Work closely with the industry/service providers to create the best solutions for public sector needs (requires prior identification of needs and requirements).
- *Security*: Maintain a continuously high level of security through technological advances and staff training.

Recommendation 7:

Using 'e-identities (and e-signatures)' to meet the public sector need 'digitization'

Status quo:

There are already many countries in the EU that have introduced e-identities, e.g. in Belgium, several Scandinavian countries, Italy, Germany, Spain, Croatia to mention just few.

These cards are used for different services within the public sector in the individual countries: for banks, for universities etc. In Estonia the ID card is even used for internet-based voting systems.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

In general it can be observed that the main challenge regarding the use of e-identities is not a technical one.

Some persisting challenges include

- Interoperability challenges (multiple identity schemes applied on a per-sector/per-country basis – multitude of standards used and lack of a commonly accepted one).

Non-technical challenges:

- *Infrastructure*: The public organization needs to procure the e-ID infrastructure itself and possibly further components like the e-identity cards for the citizens.
- *Change of processes*: The processes of the public sector organizations have to be adapted to the usage of e.g. e-identity authorization processes.
- *Cyber security issues*: The public sector organizations have to deal with cyber security issues or implement the necessary security regulations.
- *Information of the public* about the potential uses e-identity systems

Recommendation 8:

Using 'Internet of Things' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Status quo:

There are several applications of the IoT technology in the area of Health, the latter pertaining to providing assistance to people or enabling automated medication and maintenance of medical devices. According to Dimitrov, "devices and mobile apps are now increasingly used and integrated with telemedicine and telehealth via the medical Internet of Things (mIoT)". Potential applications of the IoT technology in the domain of health care include i. Remote health monitoring; ii. Emergency notification systems / contacting the hospital in case of emergencies; iii. Telemedicine; iv. Early detection of and warning about patients at risk.

* Dimitrov DV (2013) Medical Internet of Things and Big Data in Healthcare.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Tackling security concerns regarding the protection of sensitive information as well as that of human lives and health;
- Ensuring connectivity – creation of meshes with no single point of failure (IoT networks' decentralization or development of peer-to-peer ecosystems);
- Addressing compatibility & longevity challenges – development of common IoT standards, including network protocols, communication protocols and data aggregation standards.

Non-technical challenges:

Training: Train developers on the threats of IoT programming and thereby the production of both secure and functional applications;
Promotion: Educate end users on best practices around the use of IoT devices for improving privacy and security;
Data privacy: Develop regulations around the ownership of data and how it is used; Develop strategies to respect individual privacy choices across a broad spectrum of expectations, while still fostering innovation in new technologies and services.

Recommendation 9:

Using '*Machine Learning*' to meet the societal need '*Inclusive well-being and health*'

Status quo:

The following solutions are available for implementing machine learning applications:

- AmazonML (Amazon Machine Learning)
- AzureML (Azure Machine Learning)
- BigML
- Google Prediction API, a Machine Learning black box for devs
- Wise, Machine Learning for Customer Success

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Data availability and reliability; data sets upon which machine learning systems are to be trained must be unbiased and of good quality.

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training*: users need to be trained in order for machine learning applications to produce reliable results.

Recommendation 10:

Using 'Natural Language Processing' to meet the public sector need 'Digitization'

Status quo:

There are several NLP solutions on the market, such as Clarabridge NLP, RASA NLU, Ignitho NLP, NLP Technologies, Data Genic NLP, Vocali.

Potential applications of the NLP technology which could cater for the need of the public sector for further digitization include:

- Conversational interfaces
- Automated online assistants
- Sentiment analysis
- Native language identification

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Resolution of semantics and pragmatics issues (finding the meaning of a word or a word sense, determining scopes of quantifiers, finding referents of anaphora, relation of modifiers to nouns and identifying meaning of tenses to temporal objects);
- Development of domain-specific ontologies;
- Development of language-specific dictionaries;
- Development of efficient, large-scale solutions.

Non-technical challenges:

Training: cultivate expertise in data science and related fields to effectively analyse text/speech and build efficient models and ontologies.

Recommendation 11:

Using 'Wearables' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Status quo:

Examples of applications/products include Apple iOS 8 HealthKit, Live!y, BodyGuardian, Alarm.com, ActiveProtective, VitalConnect Band, Medical Wearable Solutions Eyeforcer, oRoti Labs Limited W/Me2, Cardio family of products, Biovotion AG monitoring platform.

Potential use cases involve any device or application that collects healthy aging data, mental data and social data and concern:

- Sensory integration (helping people see better or understand the world better)
- Health care monitoring systems

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Progressing with power consumption issues (equipping devices with longer battery duration);
- Advancing the design and the aesthetic aspects of wearable devices;
- Ensuring the quality of the devices' operation (eliminate heat and precipitation factors);
- Development of appropriate standards and standardized descriptions of the artefacts measured.

Non-technical challenges:

- *Safety performance*: establish binding rules, to cover safety and performance requirements of quasi-medical devices;
- *Data protection*: enable users to make privacy-friendly choices when using wearable devices;
- *Cyber security*: Adapt the legal framework to safeguard the privacy of end-users and their data-eliminate the risk of hacking and thus misusing wearable devices and the data they contain.

Recommendation 12:

Using 'Virtual Reality' to meet the societal need 'Experiential education and training' and the public sector need 'Recruitment and training'

Status quo:

Existing solutions include Google Cardboard, Samsung Gear VR and Oculus Rift in terms of hardware, and in terms of software platforms (for schools and universities) Immerse VR Education, Altrange VR and Unimersiv. The number of applications for virtual reality training is increasing over time. Thus, also special applications for the public sector (e.g. in the health area or in the area of emergency management) are possible. VR supported training use cases within the context of the public sector may indicatively include medical training / surgery simulation, architectural walkthroughs, historical re-enactments, emergency services (paramedic training), combat training, rescue teams training, professional and citizens training for crisis situations, Virtual tours and field trips to museums, landmarks or even outer space, etc.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Identification of more natural ways for users to interact with virtual reality systems;
- Design of quality virtual reality solutions for domain specific training purposes;
- Adaption and reuse of existing VR systems;
- Ensuring platform and components compatibility.

Non-technical challenges:

- Health:* Exploration of the long-term effects of VR in health.
- Cost:* Develop new, more effective and cheaper models for the incorporation of virtual reality systems in public sector practices and related training contexts.
- Promotion:* Develop a strategy to promote virtual reality to the general public.

Recommendation 13:

Using 'API Economy' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to PS services'

Status quo:

Today, APIs play a central role in integrating companies with providers, suppliers and customers. API economy related to PS services refers mainly to the public sector itself releasing open data which in turn can be consumed by businesses through APIs to provide value to citizens and potentially earn some revenue.

Everyday uses of this can be businesses that want to access traffic data to find opportunities for marketing (e.g. to people stuck in traffic). Infrastructure planning and zoning are also potential consumers of this data. Population and census data can be made available via APIs for outside developers to access and use in their Apps in creative ways.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Expansion of critical channels that need to be protected
- Deploy real-time analytics broadly, by moving analytics to the data
- Ancillary components required: documentation, code samples, testing and certification tools, support models, monitoring, maintenance, and upkeep

Non-technical challenges:

- 'data first' approach to unlock all data from current applications in the PS.
- *Marketplace*: Create a data marketplace where different creators and consumers of data can buy, sell, request or freely exchange data
- *Privacy and security concerns* arise whenever public sector entities share data, especially citizen data.
- *Data ownership and liability*, regardless of whether the APIs are open or protected.
- *Processes*: Creating the API economy in the public sector will require executive-level leadership and governance. PS leaders will need to champion API initiatives in order to overcome organizational inertia.

Recommendation 14:

Using 'Crowdsourcing' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Status quo:

Currently, crowdsourcing applied **in** the public sector refers to obtaining needed services, ideas, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group of people, especially an online community, rather than from employees or suppliers. To meet the need 'Civil servants as a community of change', crowdsourcing is to be applied **within** the public sector. This means government setting up a microtasking platform, not just for citizen engagement, but as a way to harness the knowledge and skills of its own workers across multiple departments and agencies.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Working remotely from different locations poses a major security risk. Virtual team members could be accessing sensitive information from their homes or from public Wi-Fi networks

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training:* To broaden public employees' skills and the ability to handle multiple tasks and work on a variety of projects, learning should focus on social and collaborative processes in a distributed workplace
- *Processes:* Some changes to current human resource norms focusing on flexible work arrangements are needed
- *Organisation:* The way in which individual contributions are planned, assigned, coordinated and appraised must be carefully addressed

Recommendation 15:

Using 'Digitalization' to meet the public sector need 'Increase resource productivity'

Status quo:

Digital transformation promises great things for the public sector and the citizens it serves, from lower costs and greater efficiency to real-time services, seamless communication and enhanced program effectiveness. Shared services, greater collaboration and integration, improved fraud management and productivity enhancements enable system-wide efficiencies.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- An increasingly mobile workforce can expose government networks to additional vulnerabilities
- Legacy IT systems can be risky to replace with new ones but public sector must upgrade, connect and consolidate its infrastructure before it becomes obsolete and unable to support digital and collaborative environments

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training:* The complexity of large-scale digital projects requires specialized skills and expertise, as well as a strong central leadership
- *Security:* It's critical to make online security simple for citizens while maintaining strong protections for their private data.
- *Processes:* It is a challenge to maintain strategic continuity even as political administrations change
- *Organization:* Silos, fragmentation, and the absence of a central owner for nationwide IT infrastructure and common components make it difficult to invest at scale and generate sufficient economies.
- *Ethical issues:* Digital divide in the citizenry

Recommendation 16:

Using 'e-participation' to meet the societal need 'Participative access to public sector services (political participation)'

Status quo:

In general it can be observed that the main challenge regarding the use of e-participation technologies to promote the political participation of the citizens is not a technical one.

There are already many e-participation platforms in several EU states up and running, e.g. in Estland, several Scandinavian countries, UK, Germany, Spain to mention just view. Sometimes these applications are used on a national level and sometimes on a local one (e.g. in Frankfurt, Reykjavik, Gothenburg).

Additionally there are running e-participation platforms on a European level, like the European Citizens Initiative or the Online EU Public Consultations among others.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- anonymity or real name policies; the challenge of fake profiles
- Reduction of complexity; improvement of user-friendliness & user-experience; appealing and yet simple, attractive and easy to use system
- Appropriateness for the targeted participants
- Accessibility

Non-technical challenges:

- *transparency, accountability*: Create a process how to guarantee that the opinions of the citizens are taken into consideration in the policy process
- *personnel resources*: as moderator for e-participation applications, as user support or help desk
- *promotion*: encouraging citizens to participate
- *cyber security*: e.g. prevent manipulation by organized groups, privacy, data protection, confidentiality, secure system
- *guidelines*: Develop guidelines for safe and acceptable use
- *e-identification*: harmonized rules for identification requirements

Recommendation 17:

Using 'Gamification' to meet the public sector need 'Employee remuneration and incentives'

Status quo:

Generally speaking, gamification can be part of every organization's digital business strategy. Within the public sector, gamification can be used to help public agencies run communication campaigns, raise awareness of new or undervalued initiatives, engage citizens, train officials and even change behaviour. To meet the need 'Employee remuneration and incentives', gamification can be used as a way to motivate public employees. Adding game elements to the job is expected to raise motivation, as players take on challenges, receive immediate feedback on their performance, and can compete against others. Building self-esteem and re-enforcing it with peer recognition is a powerful means of unlocking motivation.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Cyber security, as gamified processes generate a track record of employees' achievements and the collection and use of personally identifiable data

Non-technical challenges:

- *Process*: The challenge does not lie in the infrastructure, but in the design of the game. It requires a solid and user-centred process (fun scenario building a genuine sense of competition)
- *Acceptance*: There are gamification detractors that fear it's just another form of control.
- *Organisation*: Games by their nature must be voluntary, so when a department insists its employees play along, it stops being a game to be a form of coercion
- *Social issue*: With regards to peer relationships, efforts to increase internal competition could provoke employees to actively sabotage each other or make unethical choices

Recommendation 18:

Using 'Mobile devices' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to PS services'

Status quo:

The growing number of mobile devices among the citizens and the use of e-government apps improves the access to governmental services.

The number of mobile devices in the public sector itself will also lead to a growing usage of apps and thus to a further improvement of mobile governmental services.

Some examples are ECIM Smart Mobility API; Gov2go app (personal government assistant); Commercial Driver License (CDL) practice knowledge test mobile application; Whim, Mobility-as-a-Service App, linking all transport networks in Finland and suggesting travel routes using all available means of transport.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

Most preparatory technical activities need to be carried out within the restructuring and change of the given ICT structure in a country. If this is not done correctly the overall implementation of mobile devices in the public sector will not be possible. The ICT structure has to be transferred into some kind of medianet with a sufficient bandwidth for different collaborative services. One condition for this is that connectivity can be achieved in all kinds of regions, even in rural areas.

Non-technical challenges:

- *Costs*: The technologies have to be within a reasonable cost limit so everyone can use it, so relatively cheap solutions have to be found/be developed.
- *Training*: It is important to prepare training for the public and for employees of the public sector.
- *Guidelines and fact sheets*: have to be produced as well to fully inform the public and to minimize the risk of a failing societal acceptance.
- *Rules*: The consequences of this new dimension of connectivity have to be thought through and common practices have to be changed. To regulate the misuse of this mobility, new practices and rules have to be developed and introduced.

Recommendation 19:

Using *'Open data & Open Government'* to meet the business need *'Entrepreneurial and start-up culture'*

Status quo:

Open data could help entrepreneurs to find necessary information about a specific region or economic or legislative conditions or they may be used as an input for the delivery of service.

There are a lot of initiatives which provide businesses with public sector information e.g.: EU Open Data Portal; European Data portal; Policy Compass Portal; Public Contracts; Open Coesione; Visual OPML; RES (Research and Education Space); 3icity initiative of the Innovation Action Line Digital Cities; Good Basic Data for Everyone" initiative in Denmark; Publicspending.net.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Digitalization of current processes in order to streamline the process of data generation
- Adoption of an open-by-design principle allowing data to be born open thus allowing to get rid of a "data liberation" approach currently still necessary due to the close approach with which data are produced.
- Promotion of semantically enriched and machine readable outputs

Non-technical challenges:

- *Size is not synonymous of value.* That is to say, the assessment of data value should be based on a plurality of criteria: relevance for decision making, quality, availability overtime to name a few.
- *Openness* is a key. Data should be released in formats maximizing the opportunities for the generation of economies of scope.
- *Move beyond retrofitting.* Rather than liberating data ex-post, the processes of data generation have to be open-by-design.
- *Shared and clear values.* The exploitation of open data should be driven by shared values in terms of advancing the environmental, social and economic conditions of the city.

Recommendation 20:

Using 'Personalization' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Status quo:

With personalized healthcare and personalized medicine healthcare service professionals attempt to

- determine therapy and drug usage by genomic profiles
- use biological information and biomarkers to gauge the risk of disease in individuals
- provide best possible therapeutic verifiable outcome with minimal adverse effects

On the other hand, the rapid evolution of the mobile application market has become one of the most influential drivers of personalization of healthcare for consumers. The rapid growth in the use of health apps offers important trending and insights in order to consider how health systems may engage or leverage consumer's personalization of health services.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

According to the PERMED project the main technological challenges to implementing personalised medicine are integrating big data and ICT solutions and bringing innovation to the market. Further recommendations are:

- Develop new decision support tools
- Develop methods to better integrate and evaluate the information provided by genomic, epigenetic, transcriptomic, proteomic, metabolomic and micro-biome analyses.

Non-technical challenges:

According to the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the PERMED project the main non-technological challenges to implementing personalised medicine are:

- *developing awareness and empowerment*
- *integrating big data and ICT solutions*
- *translating basic research to clinical research and beyond*
- *bringing innovation to the market*
- *shaping sustainable healthcare*

Recommendation 21:

Using 'Policy Making 2.0' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Status quo:

There are already a number of platform supporting policy making 2.0 activities platforms running, both governmental ones as well as from private organisations. However, the popularity of these e-participation platforms varies from country to country: Citizen Space; Futurium; Puzzled by Policy; SOLVIT; OurSpace; Agora Voting; kosovakosovo.com (Serbia, Kosovo); OpenKratio; Policy Compass; Sirvo A Mi Pais; FUPOL applications; Better Reykjavik; Gothenburg, Online forum; The Malmö Initiative.

Existing initiatives that support policy making 2.0 already are: European Citizens' Initiative (ECI); Online EU Public Consultations; Petitions to the European Parliament

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

The technological activities conducted to be conducted in the field of policy making 2.0 should focus on pushing forward the state of the art for the following enabling technologies :

- Big data; Opinion mining and sentiment analysis; Visual analytics for collaborative governance; Serious gaming for behavioural change; Linked open government data; Participatory sensing; Block chain; Global System science

Non-technical challenges:

The activities aimed at improving the public value generated by policy making 2.0 solutions will have to be aimed at attaining the following objectives:

- increase the *pro-activeness* of policy making in dealing with societal issue before they reach unmanageable sizes and/or chronic phases,
- improve the *reactiveness* in dealing with unexpected abrupt events,
- *reduce the gap* between expected outcomes and delivered results.
- The main challenge will be in striking the right *balance* in the collaboration between algorithms and humans in the definition of new decision making processes.

Recommendation 22:

Using 'Smart Workplace' to meet the business need 'Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures'

Status quo:

According to a CBRE foresight study in 2040 e.g. the following properties will characterize a smart workplace:

- Flexible working contracts (increase mobility and unconventional working patterns)
- 'wellness' services at the workplace
- Focus on collaboration

Many employees prefer to have a mobile working environment and mobile solutions to help them to improve their work-life-balance. Thus many mobile solutions (like smartphones & tablets, wearables, cloud computing) would help to attract new talents.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

There are already a lot of technologies available to enhance the work-live-balance:

- **Mobile working environments**
- **Mobile solutions: smartphones and tablets, wearables, cloud computing**
- **Communication platforms**
- **Time accounts**
- as well as various recruiting activities in **Social Media**

Non-technical challenges:

- *Strategies for acquisition and retention and training possibilities* should be developed. Stakeholders have to be aware of the future risks. A flexible smart workplace is a great possibility to acquire and retain employees that lead a family life.
- *A flexible smart workplace* additionally strengthen globalization processes while enables collaboration with partners in different time zones. So business can grow fast, and enable high-powered freelancers to emerge.
- When dealing with flexible smart workplaces the 24/7 work culture have to be covered by *regulations or a legal framework*. Otherwise health issues, like psychological disease, can be the result.

Recommendation 23:

Social Media & Social Networking

Participate access to public sector services (political participation)

Using 'Social Media & Social Networking' to meet the societal need 'Participate access to public sector services (political participation)'

Status quo:

Today as many as 152 countries out of 193 (four out of five; in Europe 39 out of 43) offer social networking features, such as the "Like" button, on their national portals (i.e. there are links to, for example, Facebook, Twitter, Sina Weibo (in China), Odnoklassniki/VK in the Russian-speaking countries, etc.)

For example in the UK 100% of the local governments use twitter, 90% Facebook, 68% YouTube, 54% Flickr and 38% Instagram.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Social media are very popular in Europe. Currently there are 412 million active users in Europe and 39 out of 43 European countries offer social networking features in their national portals.
- There are no real technological challenges, as social media services are already provided by big companies (e.g. Facebook, twitter). Current challenges persist in other areas like e.g. cyber security or issues regarding privacy and data protection.

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training*: the public sector needs personnel with the necessary digital literacy and the capacity to deal with the inputs received via social media services
- *Commitment*: to actively engage citizens via social media
- *Promotion*: the public sector organizations have to promote their social media presence
- *Cyber security* and also privacy and data protection issues are important and have to be dealt with
- *Regulations*: governments and local administrations should set up social media strategies including e.g. privacy requirements, acceptable and forbidden content, data handling, citizen engagement, etc.

4 Technology brief

One of the explicit aims of SONNETS is to inform the public sector about emerging ICTs and trends and how they can be used to modernize the public sector and addressing thereby related societal challenges.

During the course of SONNETS we have identified 23 technologies and trends which have the potential to innovate the public sector. This technology brief contains a set of 23 one-pagers with a summary of recommendations for each of the identified technologies.

Each of these one-page recommendations contains an emerging technology or trend and the suggestion to implement this technology with the aim to satisfy a specific societal, business or public sector need.

For each of these technologies we have performed a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis to present the respective advantages and drawbacks of the usage of these technologies in the public sector.

Recommendation 1:

Artificial Intelligence & bots

Access to public sector information

Using 'artificial intelligence and bots' to meet the business need 'Access to public sector information'

Actual solutions and services:

In general it can be observed that artificial intelligence is one of the top emerging technologies in which a lot of research and development is happening right now.

However, the state of the art of artificial intelligence already permits to have several applications which could help to satisfy the need to access public sector information.

There are already many administrations, like Enfield Council, the Department of Homeland Security, North Carolina's Innovation Center, the Australian Tax Office or the government of Singapore which use artificial intelligence in the form of chatbots to interact with their citizens.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overcoming the limitations of human nature (not limited by fatigue, boredom or emotions intercepting rational thinking). Undertaking laborious tasks – reducing human effort. Convenience – making daily life a lot easier with its several applications (auto-correct apps, personal assistants, gps, etc.) Saving the need of organisations for human resources. Carrying out repetitive and time-consuming tasks efficiently. Capable of carrying out dangerous or risky tasks. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethical and moral issues, found in embedding intelligence in a machine. Significant maintenance and repair costs to suit changing requirements. Lacking common sense, creativity, intuitiveness and the human touch. Difficulty in ensuring that AI will be used ethically. Not as efficient as humans in adapting responses, depending on changing situations.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Public Services Assistance. Intelligent Agents for Policy Decisions Automation in mainstream tasks 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hesitancy in fully delegating important tasks to AI applications. Fear of replacing humans in their job positions /unemployment. Fear of lateral thinking and multitasking abilities of humans gradually declining due to the reduced need to use their intelligence - humans becoming overly dependent on machines. Fear of destructive consequences if control of AI goes to the wrong hands. Fear of smart machines superseding and enslaving humans.

Recommendation 2:

Using 'augmented reality' to meet the societal need 'Experiential education and training'

Actual solutions and services:

According to Gartner augmented reality (AR) belongs to the key technology trends and is showing promise in delivering a high degree of competitive advantage over the next five to 10 years.

But already now there are a lot of augmented reality apps for the classroom, which are also in use in some schools. In the French curriculum augmented reality is already recommended to be used in middle school.

Also more specialized AR systems for university students or in the automotive or printing industry exist. In a military environment AR has been used since 2009.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a more interactive and personal experience. • Allowing to experience the word at one's ease and convenience. • Improving mobile usability by acting as the interface itself, requiring little interaction. • Enabling more cost-effective and risk-free training – allowing to simulate practices without to actually expose people to risky situations or hazardous environments. • Advancing and facilitating education (visualize “difficult” to explain concepts, facilitate learners' interaction, apply trial and error methods, etc.). • Providing real-time feedback. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hampering the interaction with the real world – replacing human interaction. • Still facing technical challenges and limitations. The accurate tracking of the position and the line of sight of the user are still challenging aspects. However, this is important for the accuracy of the alignment of the virtual objects on the real world).
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public employees training. • Safer and informative navigation. • Aiding disabled people by providing vital information, otherwise cumbersome to obtain and enhancing their environment. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Individual) privacy concerns – probability of access to information that one should not readily possess about a given person. • High development costs • Need for investments in wearables

Recommendation 3:

Big data & data analytics

Inclusive well-being and health

Using 'big data and data analytics' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Actual solutions and services:

Big Data technologies will definitely open new opportunities and enable breakthroughs related to healthcare data analytics addressing different perspectives: (i) descriptive to answer what happened, (ii) diagnostic to answer the reason why it happened, (iii) predictive to understand what will happen and (iv) prescriptive to detect how we can make it happen.

There are already many examples for the application of big data analytics in health care up and running ranging from applications for asthma patients, treatments for cancer patients, rare diseases, to the personnel planning in emergency rooms.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster, better decision making. • Informed and often real time insights on issues of interest. • Development of new products and services. • Ever-narrower segmentation of customers and therefore much more precisely tailored products or services. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using real-time insights requires a different way of working within organisations. • Data quality concerns. • Imperfect methodology issues – questionable quality of predictions.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better simulation services for the Public Sector • Development of improved health care services • 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy concerns.

Recommendation 4:

Using 'biometrics' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Actual solutions and services:

Biometric methods are used in many different areas of applications. The solutions and systems available on the market are able to serve a broad range regarding performance, security, usability and standard conformance.

Many EU countries already use biometric identity cards (e.g. Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands) or biometric visa programs. Some EU countries use biometric ID cards for social security systems, requesting car licence plates or conducting tax declarations.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique and accurate identification • Accountability (clear, definable audit trail of transactions) • Time saving (a person can be identified in seconds) • Convenience and user friendliness • Higher degree of security than traditional authentication methods • Versatility (several types of biometric scanners available). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost • Cannot be cancelled or replaced by a new version as passwords or tokens. • Offending human dignity (turning the human subject into a collection of biometric parameters, dehumanizing the person, infringing bodily integrity). • Low social acceptability/User resistance.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel identification and authentication schemes • Improved public sector services security. • Assistance for impaired people. • International sharing of biometric data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy and data protection concerns • Discrimination concerns (Soft biometrics traits complementing the identity information provided by the primary biometric identifiers are strongly cultural based.) • The accuracy of biometric recognition technologies depends on the user and on environmental conditions

Recommendation 5:

Blockchain technology

Faster and transparent access to public sector services

Using 'blockchain technology' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Actual solutions and services:

There are many possible ways that blockchains can make government more accountable, transparent, efficient and fraud-proof, which include contract management, electronic voting and health care.

There are already several pilot projects in different countries regarding the use of block chain technology in e-health, e-resident systems, elections and especially land and property registration.

A prominent country which has already several applications of blockchain technology in use is Estonia. Other countries include for example Sweden, Hong Kong, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria or Georgia.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trustful exchanges without the oversight or intermediation of a third party. High quality data - blockchain data is complete, consistent, timely, accurate, and widely available. Durability, reliability, and longevity. Process integrity – transactions executed exactly as the protocol commands. Transparency and immutability Ecosystem simplification - single public ledger, instead of multiple ones. Faster transactions – transactions are processed 24/7 Lower transaction costs - third party intermediaries and overhead costs are eliminated. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irreversible transactions. Nascent technology - challenges exist with regard to transaction volume and speed, the verification process, and data limits (data storage). Uncertain regulatory status, impeding widespread adoption. Large energy consumption High initial capital costs. Concerns on control, security, and privacy. Integration concerns - significant changes to, or complete replacement of, existing systems are needed. Complex to implement and maintain (especially private blockchains).
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Verify integrity of transactions. Reduce fraud and corruption. Openness and Transparency Distributed Control of Operations 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Widespread adoption is challenging. Blockchain's linkage with illegal activities. Large scale deployments are necessary to ensure integrity.

Recommendation 6:

Cloud computing

Faster and transparent access to public sector services

Using 'cloud computing' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Actual solutions and services:

There are already many cloud providers available, like e.g.

- Public clouds (e.g. Google docs, Microsoft Office 365, SAP Business by Design)
- Private Clouds
- Hybrid Clouds (have elements of private and public cloud)
- Infrastructure as a service (IaaS) (e.g. Amazon Web Services, Google Compute Engine, Windows Azure)
- Platform as a service (PaaS) (e.g. Google App Engine, Amazon Elastic Beanstalk)
- Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) (e.g. from Microsoft, Google, Salesforce.com, Cisco, Intuit)

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High computing power and performance • Agility and flexibility • Scalability and elasticity • Productivity (capability of users simultaneous work on the same data) • Device and location independence • Portability across devices • Cost reductions (operational expenditure instead of capital expenditure, lower needs for in-house IT skills, lower maintenance costs) • Improved security (at central level) 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of legislative framework about cloud services • Loss of control over sensitive data • Non strict SLAs
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low infrastructure Costs • Ability to open up services and data • Data Resilience and Sharing • Big data analytics enablement • Low Cost for testing and development environments • Vendor independence 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insecure Interfaces and API's • Data Loss & Leakage • Risk of vendor lock-in in certain cases • Vagueness around legal ownership of the data • DevOps roles necessary • Unexpectedly high charges (e.g. ingress of data might be free, but extracting it can be costly)

Recommendation 7:

Using 'e-identities (and e-signatures)' to meet the public sector need 'digitization'

Actual solutions and services:

There are already many countries in the EU that have introduced e-identities, e.g. in Belgium, several Scandinavian countries, Italy, Germany, Spain, Croatia to mention just view.

These cards are used for different services within the public sector in the individual countries: for banks, for universities etc. In Estonia the ID card is even used for internet-based voting systems.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting e-services and customized service-delivery. • Improving security in terms of accountability • Increasing administrative efficiency and reducing cost (diminishing manual/repetitive work and interactions). • Limiting possibilities for fraud, identity theft and phishing. • Supporting mutual recognition of documents and certificates in cross-border situations. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs of the eID infrastructure itself and organisational costs (card issuance and cardholder enrolment).
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Access to Services • Global Identification Services Potentially improving national security. • Building a more inclusive European society (a seamless use of eID should offer EU wide service provision). • Stimulating the introduction of new e-services and generating economies of scale, as eID is part of an 'infrastructural approach'. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy concerns for end users. • Interoperability challenges (multiple identity schemes applied on a per-sector/per-country basis – multitude of standards used and lack of a commonly accepted one. • Legal difficulties (different legal frameworks on a per-country basis) in case of a cross-country infrastructure. • High costs for securing identity registries

Recommendation 8:

Internet of things

Inclusive well-being and health

Using 'internet of things' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Actual solutions and services:

There are several applications of the IoT technology in the area of Health, the latter pertaining to providing assistance to people or enabling automated medication and maintenance of medical devices.

According to Dimitrov, "devices and mobile apps are now increasingly used and integrated with telemedicine and telehealth via the medical Internet of Things (mIoT)".

Potential applications of the IoT technology in the domain of health care include i. Remote health monitoring; ii. Emergency notification systems / contacting the hospital in case of emergencies; iii. Telemedicine; iv. Early detection of and warning about patients at risk.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced connectivity of devices, systems and services beyond machine-to-machine communications. • Advanced levels of automation, control and monitoring (avoiding human intervention). • Availability of more information and better decision making. • Higher Efficiency, Safety and Comfort. • Covering a variety of protocols, domains, and applications. • Enabling advanced applications • Shorter reaction times. • Context awareness. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compatibility/interoperability issues – platform fragmentation and lack of a common standard. • Complexity – more opportunities of failure/failures may have serious consequences. • Single point of vulnerability of multiple systems. • Batteries dependency. • Fewer requirements in human resources – rise of unemployment. • Creating dependence of daily life upon technology.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better Human-Machine integration for public services • Empowering Big Data • Generation of dynamic and distributed information. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical safety in case of private and confidential information being accessed by unauthorized intruders. • Privacy and security issues. • Issues around the ownership of data and how the latter is used.

Recommendation 9:

Machine learning

Inclusive well-being and health

Using '*Machine learning*' to meet the societal need '*Inclusive well-being and health*'

Actual solutions and services:

The following solutions are available for implementing machine learning applications:

- AmazonML (Amazon Machine Learning)
- AzureML (Azure Machine Learning)
- BigML
- Google Prediction API, a Machine Learning black box
- Wise, Machine Learning for Customer Success

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce reliable, repeatable decisions and results. • Uncover "hidden insights" through learning from historical relationships and trends in the data. • Faster processing than the human brain. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor results if not investing in training • Technology not advancing in the paces expected
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value extraction from large volumes of data currently underexploited. • Identification of weak signals and patterns. • Intelligent Service Providers 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machine ethics - Systems which are trained on datasets collected with biases may exhibit these biases upon use, thus digitizing cultural prejudices such as institutional racism and classism. Responsible collection of data thus is a critical part of machine learning.

Recommendation 10:

Using 'Natural Language Processing' to meet the public sector need 'Digitization'

Actual solutions and services:

There are several NLP solutions on the market, such as Clarabridge NLP, RASA NLU, Ignitho NLP, NLP Technologies, Data Genic NLP, Vocali.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced customer experience. Improved documentation efficiency and accuracy. Identification of the most pertinent information from large databases. Contextual understanding. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Domain specific ontologies required. Language specific dictionaries required. Difficulty to identify irony.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perspectives and perceptions identification. Extraction of value from large volumes of data currently underexploited. Fighting Digital Divide 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government rules and regulations hindering natural language processing solutions to be widely adapted. Need for smart devices, web & cloud-based applications. Privacy Considerations

Recommendation 11:

Using 'Wearables' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Actual solutions and services:

Examples of applications/products include Apple iOS 8 HealthKit, Live!y, BodyGuardian, Alarm.com, ActiveProtective, VitalConnect Band, Medical Wearable Solutions Eyeforcer, oRoti Labs Limited W/Me2, Cardio family of products, Biovotion AG monitoring platform.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience of use (hands-free). • Personal safety improvement. • Health and fitness tracking - Real-time monitoring and information provision to health providers. • Ensuring better engagement with the environment. • Endless possibilities for connectivity with other devices. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive. • Not as widely accepted- • Heat and precipitation can damage wearable devices. • Power management (constrained power reserves-short battery life) and heat dissipation issues affecting the quality and trust of the devices. • Not widely accepted – awkward for some.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved service personalisation • Retrieval of sensory information about individuals • Compensating disabilities or supporting elderly people in public services/buildings. • Providing info in sites of interest through VR or augmented reality. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invading privacy of other people. • Potential misuse of private (biometric/physiological/health) data. • Risk of hacking and thus misusing wearable devices.

Recommendation 12:

Using 'Virtual Reality' to meet the societal need 'Experiential education and training' and the public sector need 'Recruitment and training'

Actual solutions and services:

Existing solutions include Google Cardboard, Samsung Gear VR and Oculus Rift in terms of hardware, and in terms of software platforms (for schools and universities) Immerse VR Education, Altrange VR and Unimersiv.

Also special applications for the public sector (e.g. in the health area or in the area of emergency management) are possible. VR supported training use cases within the context of the public sector may indicatively include medical training / surgery simulation, architectural walkthroughs, historical re-enactments, emergency services (paramedic training), combat training, rescue teams training, professional and citizens training for crisis situations, Virtual tours and field trips to museums, landmarks or even outer space, etc.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulating the real world – realistic scenarios • Stimulus Control and Consistency. • Immersive experience. • Convenience-remote engagement, also saving time and money. • Safe Testing and Training Environment - modelling complex task-performance behaviours, many of which carry life-or-death risks in real-world learning. • Cuing Stimuli to Support "Error-Free Learning". • Self-Guided Exploration and Independent Practice. • Real-Time Performance Feedback. • Gaming Factors to Enhance Motivation. • Patient rehabilitation. • Innovative and enjoyable. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High price. • Technical challenges (e.g. platform compatibility). • Interface-related challenges (cables impeding movement, poorly designed instruments causing fatigue and an unsettling feeling of enclosure). • Prolonged use side-effects (sickness, headache, vertigo, nausea, disorientation etc.). • Individuals having a hard time deciphering what is real and what is virtual. • Faulty training results in case of poor models of the real world.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public organizations employees training. • Citizen's Training. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of not wide use and acceptance. • High investments costs. • Health threats.

Recommendation 13:

Using 'API Economy' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Actual solutions and services:

Today, APIs play a central role in integrating companies with providers, suppliers and customers. API economy related to PS services refers mainly to the public sector itself releasing open data which in turn can be consumed by businesses through APIs to provide value to citizens and potentially earn some revenue.

Everyday uses of this can be businesses that want to access traffic data to find opportunities for marketing (e.g. to people stuck in traffic). Infrastructure planning and zoning are also potential consumers of this data. Population and census data can be made available via APIs for outside developers to access and use in their Apps in creative ways.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of applications pertaining to different domains • Reliability and user friendliness • Speed of new developments • Reusability • Efficiency and automation of work 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming knowledge required • Poor or badly written APIs • Associated costs (development costs, maintenance costs, API documentation, support provision to users of the API) • Maintenance required • Potential of system crash when testing APIs • No standardised documentation
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of innovative online services for citizens and businesses • Cross-sector integration • More integrated user experience • Entrepreneurship and innovation acceleration • Exposure of Public Data and Services to third parties • Personalization 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security exposure / security concerns - API vulnerabilities may be used by hackers • Improper use of APIs by third parties • High utilisation of Public Sector infrastructures

Recommendation 14:

Crowdsourcing

Civil servants as a community of change

Using 'Crowdsourcing' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Actual solutions and services:

Currently, crowdsourcing applied in the public sector refers to obtaining needed services, ideas, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group of people, especially an online community, rather than from employees or suppliers. To meet the need 'Civil servants as a community of change', crowdsourcing is to be applied **within** the public sector. This means government setting up a microtasking platform, not just for citizen engagement, but as a way to harness the knowledge and skills of its own workers across multiple departments and agencies.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to new pools of external talent and expertise from a diversity of fields • Reduced cost of conducting research and development • Less cost compared to outsourcing • Incorporation of end users/customers early in the development process • Faster design and prototyping • Potential for higher quality • Increased agility and faster time to market 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruiting and retaining users can be a challenge • Types of users' contributions are mostly limited (e.g. review/rate/tag/etc.) • Difficulty in combining and evaluating user contributions - unstructured information gathered, cumbersome to filter • Good quality of user contributions is not guaranteed • Difficulty in keeping hold of confidential information and intellectual property
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective Intelligence • Co-creation and collaboration for needs tackling 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical concerns • Private Data Exposure • IPR issues

Recommendation 15:

Using 'Digitalization' to meet the public sector need 'Increase resource productivity'

Actual solutions and services:

Digital transformation promises great things for the public sector and the citizens it serves, from lower costs and greater efficiency to real-time services, seamless communication and enhanced program effectiveness. Shared services, greater collaboration and integration, improved fraud management and productivity enhancements enable system-wide efficiencies.

We can mention as an example:

- STORK project
- PAE (Portal Administracion electronica)
- Cita Previa de Atención Primaria (online medical appointment)
- Agencia Tributaria

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering more communication and transaction channels • Convenience – enabling access through a digital device • Flexibility in manipulating information • Innovation • Scalability • Speed of doing business 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High initial investment and maintenance costs • Availability of digital equipment (e.g. computer) needed • Digital literacy and competence needed both in the back-office and in the front desk
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalisation of public services • Use of electronic files and electronic records • 24/7 services availability • Increased system interoperability • Information and service reuse • Economies of scale enabled. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes required in both processes and IT systems of the public sector • Digital illiteracy of public sector employees and citizens • Resistance to change • Security and vulnerability threats

Recommendation 16:

Using 'e-participation' to meet the societal need 'Participative access to public sector services (political participation)'

Actual solutions and services:

There are already many e-participation platforms in several EU states up and running, e.g. in Estland, several Scandinavian countries, UK, Germany, Spain to mention just view. Sometimes these applications are used on a national level and sometimes on a local one (e.g. in Frankfurt, Reykjavik, Gothenburg). Additionally there are running e-participation platforms on a European level, like the European Citizens Initiative or the Online EU Public Consultations among others.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active citizenship. • Engagement and empowerment of people with mobility problems. • Enhanced transparency and increased acceptance of political decisions (e.g. with regard to planning processes, cost savings, etc.). • Reducing democratic deficit. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet access and familiarity with e-participation technologies as prerequisites. • Lack of participants' identification. • Resolutions often not considered seriously by decision makers
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternative forms of engagement and (young) people's disengagement in 'traditional' politics. • Non discrimination of participants • Technological advancements in ICTs, which make traditional democratic institutions look sluggish, irresponsible and 'outdated'. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital divide (both in terms of digital infrastructure and in terms of citizens' experience with e-participation). • Manipulation by organised groups (especially in small scale applications). • Online propaganda. • If not properly addressed, e-participation can be frustrating for the citizenship.

Recommendation 17:

Using 'Gamification' to meet the public sector need 'Employee remuneration and incentives'

Actual solutions and services:

Generally speaking, gamification can be part of every organization's digital business strategy. Within the public sector, gamification can be used to help public agencies run communication campaigns, raise awareness of new or undervalued initiatives, engage citizens, train officials and even change behaviour. To meet the need 'Employee remuneration and incentives', gamification can be used as a way to motivate public employees. Adding game elements to the job is expected to raise motivation, as players take on challenges, receive immediate feedback on their performance, and can compete against others. Building self-esteem and re-enforcing it with peer recognition is a powerful means of unlocking motivation.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of a minimal shared language, which enables simplicity and speed in implementation by designers, facilitates widespread adoption by services and systems far away from the entertainment world and shortens the learning curve for users. • Availability of ready-to-use solutions • Enhanced user engagement and motivation 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear effects on user attitudes and behaviours. • One-size-fits-all approach that impedes customization of the game mechanics for specific user groups • Legal restrictions applying (virtual currencies and virtual assets, data privacy laws and data protection, or labour laws) • High development costs • Need for expertise in information systems, organization behaviour and human psychology.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing behaviour towards better practices • Increasing IT literacy skills of users 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure by poor design • Behaviour manipulation and ethical issues – promotion of mechanical behaviours without any improvement of the user experience • Unrealistic expectations

Recommendation 18:

Mobile devices

Faster and transparent access to PS services

Using 'Mobile devices' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to PS services'

Actual solutions and services:

The growing number of mobile devices among the citizens and the use of e-government apps improves the access to governmental services. The number of mobile devices in the public sector itself will also lead to a growing usage of apps and thus to a further improvement of mobile governmental services.

Some examples are:

- ECIM Smart Mobility API
- Gov2go app (personal government assistant)
- Commercial Driver License (CDL) practice knowledge test mobile application
- Whim, Mobility-as-a-Service App, linking all transport networks in Finland and suggesting travel routes using all available means of transport

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of communication. • Flexibility and dynamicity. • Portability. • Efficiency. • Support for several applications – all-in-one device. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet access required for certain functions. • Variable connectivity. • Hindering real human interaction. • Increasing the probability of accidents.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Services reaching more people. • Increased personalisation opportunities. • Increased sensory data collection. • Enablement of novel technologies related to mobile devices (wearables, biometrics, eIDs, etc.). 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyberattacks and security breaches. • Privacy and Personal Data. • Vendor lock-in.

Recommendation 19:

Open data & Open Government

Entrepreneurial and start-up culture

Using 'Open data & Open Government' to meet the business need 'Entrepreneurial and start-up culture'

Actual solutions and services:

Open data could help entrepreneurs to find necessary information about a specific region or economic or legislative conditions or they may be used as an input for the delivery of service.

There are a lot of initiatives which provide businesses with public sector information e.g.:

- EU Open Data Portal
- European Data portal
- Policy Compass Portal
- Public Contracts
- Open Coesione
- Visual OPML
- RES (Research and Education Space)
- 3cixty initiative of the Innovation Action Line Digital Cities
- Good Basic Data for Everyone" initiative in Denmark
- Publicspending.net

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced government transparency • Improved or new private products and services. • Improved efficiency and effectiveness of government services. • Technological innovation and economic growth by enabling third parties to develop new kinds of digital applications. • New knowledge from combined data sources and patterns in large data volume. • Acceleration of rate of scientific discovery by better access to data. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nowell defined standards • Lack of data validation mechanisms regarding their veracity and completeness • Collecting, 'cleaning', managing and disseminating data are typically labour- and/or cost-intensive processes. • Additional processing is often needed by targeted end-users (analysis, apps, etc.). • Little incentives to invest in the processing required to make data useful.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote birth of open data driven business ventures. • Stimulate interagency benchmarking and learning. • Generation of new business services around open data 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further advantage already privileged groups (e.g. a small elite of technical specialists or those who can afford to employ open data) -Increase the digital divide and social inequality, unless approached right. • Concern that open data will be misinterpreted

Recommendation 20:

Using 'Personalization' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Actual solutions and services:

With personalized healthcare and personalized medicine healthcare service professionals attempt to

- determine therapy and drug usage by genomic profiles
- use biological information and biomarkers to gauge the risk of disease in individuals
- provide best possible therapeutic verifiable outcome with minimal adverse effects

On the other hand, the rapid evolution of the mobile application market has become one of the most influential drivers of personalisation of healthcare for consumers. The rapid growth in the use of health apps offers important trending and insights in order to consider how health systems may engage or leverage consumer's personalization of health services.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering a better customer experience/Improving customer satisfaction. • Improving customer/user retention. • Enabling time and money savings for the user – preventing redundant work. • Providing more targeted (filtered) information. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher cost. • Anonymity may be preferred. • Lack of relevance. • Can create a "filter bubble" that prevents people from encountering a diversity of viewpoints beyond their own.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving the effectiveness of public services. • Reducing errors. • Enabling time and money savings for citizens. • Linking life events and real-time needs with services • Potential of using data from a user's personal social graph. • Fighting digital divide. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing system complexity. • Increasing service provisioning costs. • High Privacy and Ethical concerns.

Recommendation 21:

Using 'Policy Making 2.0' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Actual solutions and services:

There are already a number of platform supporting policy making 2.0 activities platforms running, both governmental ones as well as from private organisations. However, the popularity of these e-participation platforms varies from country to country: Citizen Space; Futurium; Puzzled by Policy; SOLVIT; OurSpace; Agora Voting; kosovakosovo.com (Serbia, Kosovo); OpenKratio; Policy Compass; Sirvo A Mi Pais; FUPOL applications; Better Reykjavik; Gothenburg, Online forum; The Malmö Initiative.

Existing initiatives that support policy making 2.0 already are:

- European Citizens' Initiative (ECI)
- Online EU Public Consultations
- Petitions to the European Parliament

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling all stakeholders to participate in the decision/policy making process. • Citizen engagement and democratic participation. • Enabling citizens to offer a set of unique skills and competencies (as provided by participating citizens) that government cannot acquire or can do so at high cost. • Enabling governments to acquire feedback on planned or implemented policies. • Enabling the civil society to act a watchdog for government. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in legislation needed. • High cost of implementation. • Not guaranteed participation of stakeholders involved. • Existence of bias – results and outputs may represent just a sample of the society.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More participative policy formulation. • Higher alignment between societal needs and policies implemented. • Enablement of learning processes. • Non-discriminatory participation in policy making • Transparency support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neglecting citizen's opinions • Manipulation of user groups and/or specific resolution by organised communities • One-Off approaches, not sustained • No clear Policy Making 2.0 strategy • High costs in data/information curation

Recommendation 22:

Using 'Smart Workplace' to meet the business need 'Talent acquisition and retention; Simplifying recruitment procedures'

Actual solutions and services:

According to a CBRE foresight study in 2040 e.g. the following properties will characterize a smart workplace:

- Flexible working contracts (increase mobility and unconventional working patterns)
- "wellness" services at the workplace
- Focus on collaboration

Many employees prefer to have a mobile working environment and mobile solutions to help them to improve their work-life-balance. Thus many mobile solutions (like smartphones & tablets, wearables, cloud computing) would help to attract new talents.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency and productivity. • Greater employee commitment. • Competitive advantage. • Higher degree of collaboration. • Multiple channels of communication. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High setup costs. • Skilled personnel/employees required.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better work-life balance. • Higher environmental sustainability. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change. • Bureaucracy • Privatisation of Public Assets

Recommendation 23:

Social Media & Social Networking

Participate access to public sector services (political participation)

Using 'Social Media & Social Networking' to meet the societal need 'Participate access to public sector services (political participation)'

Actual solutions and services:

Today as many as 152 countries out of 193 (four out of five; in Europe 39 out of 43) offer social networking features, such as the "Like" button, on their national portals (i.e. there are links to, for example, Facebook, Twitter, Sina Weibo (in China), Odnoklassniki/VK in the Russian-speaking countries, etc.)

For example in the UK 100% of the local governments use twitter, 90% Facebook, 68% YouTube, 54% Flickr and 38% Instagram.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving individuals' sense of connectedness with real and/or online communities. Popularity, outreach. Ease of use. Immediacy. Integration on mobile devices. 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negatively impacting social skills due to the absence of face-to-face contact Affecting mental and physical health - links found between heavy social media use and depression, sleep deprivation, addictive behaviours, etc. Becoming a factor of distraction for many users. Enabling behaviours, like cyberbullying, online harassment and "trolling". Scepticism around the reliability of user-generated content. Huge debate on the ownership of the content on social media platforms. Privacy concerns Potential of data and information collected for third party use.
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher participation opportunities. Personalised Services. Novel communication channels. Online information/data sourcing opportunities. Crowdsourcing enabler. 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exclusion of people with no social media profiles or no access to web services or even technology illiterates. Citizen data being collected for law enforcement and governmental purposes. Privacy and Ethics concerns.

5 Conclusion

SONNETS has pursued the aim to meet the need for a better, more efficient, effective and quality delivering public service. This does not only imply transforming the public sector itself and covering the needs of public sector employees and policy makers, but it will also have a positive impact on citizens and businesses, that will in turn accelerate the EU economy and improve quality of life.

Thus, the final output of SONNETS contains roadmaps of necessary research, innovation and implementation activities to modernize the public sector with emerging ICTs and addressing thereby related societal challenges.

This deliverable contains a summary of these roadmaps published in SONNETS D4.3 [5] in form of stakeholder tailored recommendation briefs. In total three briefs prepared: (I) a policy brief for policy makers and decision makers in the area of research planning; (II) a research brief for researchers and industrial stakeholders working in the area of these emerging ICTs and (III) a technology brief for decision makers in the public sector itself.

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